

Gather and Edited By

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Mcq OF Pak Geography

Best Of Luck

***You Can Not Help Every one
But Every One Can Help
Someone***

GEOGRAPHY OF PAKISTAN

- Steel Mill is in Bin Qasim
- Old name of Jacobabad is Khangharh.
- Kot Digi Fort is in Khairpur district.
- Peshawar means city of flowers.
- Warsak dam (near Peshawar) is built on Kabul River.
- Tirich Mir mounts of Hindu Kush separate Afghanistan and Tajistan from Pak:
- Islamia College Peshawar was founded in 1914 by Sahibzada Abdul Qayum.
- Quaid Azam Medical College is in Bahawalpur.
- Choukundi toms are located near Karachi.
- Atock Fort was built by Akbar.
- The land b/w Indus & Jehlum river is called Thal Desert or Sindh Sagar Doab.
- Ruins of Harapa found in Sahiwal.
- Lahore Fort was built by Akbar.
- At Toonsa Sharif the borders of three provinces meet.
- With Gilgit & Baltistan the frontiers of three counties meet.
- Tochi pass connects Pak: with China.
- Pak: has 6 international airports.
- Pak: has 27 Radio Stations.
- — district, — divisions.
- Pak: railways factory is in Risalpur.
- Chitral is famous for gold.
- Port Qasim is the largest seaport of Pak: smallest is Gawadar
- The chairman of National Economic Council is PM.
- National flower of Pakistan is Jasmine.
- National bird of Pakistan is Chakore.
- National tree of Pakistan is Deodar.
- National animal of Pakistan is Markhor (a type of goat).
- National emblem of Pakistan is Crescent.
- National sport of Pakistan is land Hockey.
- Oldest cantonment of Pak: is Kohat.
- HQ of Pak: Army is at RawalPindi.
- HQ of Airforce is at Chaklala.
- HQ of Navy is at Islamabad.
- Islamabad is 8 miles from Rawalpindi.

- Photograph on the coin of one rupee is Quaid's photo.
- "Two rupee is Badshahi Mosque (chh)
- "Ten rupee note is Khyber Pass.
- "5 rupee note is
- "50 rupee note is
- "100 is Quaid's Residency, Ziarat Quetta.
- "500 is Badshahi Mosque, Lahore.
- "100 is Jehangir's Tomb.
- "5000 is of Faisal Mosque, Islamabad.
- 4.8% of total area of Pak: is forests (standard is 25%)
- Hub dam and Thadho Dam are in Malir Karachi near Gadap Town.
- Map of Shah Faisal Mosque was made by Wahdat Diloky of Turkey.
- Largest radio station of Pak: is Islamabad.
- Tarbela dam is in Abot Abad.
- Raveewind is in Kasur.
- Baitul Maal established in 1992.
- General sales tax, under the constitution 1973 is a Federal subject.
- Pak: national flag was adopted on 11 August, 1947
- Jasmine adopted on July 5, 1961.
- National drink is Cane Juice.
- Railway stations in Pak: = 965.
- Rabi crops are grown b/w months of Oct-March.
- Under Indus Water Basin Treaty Pak: got Jehlum, Chenab & Indus. India got Ravi, Sutlaj.
- Chenab and Jehlum flow from Kashmir.
- Tirchmir is the highest peak of Hindukash.
- A bicameral legislature was proposed for the first time in 1973 constitution.
- Length of Pak-India border is 1,610 km.
- Length of Pak-Iran border is 805 km.
- Length of Pak-China border is 595 km.
- Length of Pak-Afghan border is 2052 km or 1300 miles.
- 5 rivers flow in Punjab Ravi, Sutlaj, Chenab, Indus & Beas.
- Warsak dam is on Kabul River.
- Rawal Dam is on Kurrang River.
- Khanpur dam is on Haro River.

- Tanda dam is in Baluchistan.
- Tarbela dam was completed in 1969.
- Length of Indus is 2900 km.
- Source of Indus is Mansoorowar Lake in Gilgit.
- Muztag pass connects Gilgit-Yarkand (China).
- Khankum Pass connects Chitral-Wakhan (Afghanistan)
- The Shandur Pass connects Chitral and Gilgit.
- Khyber Pass connects Peshawar-Kabul
- Kulk pass connects Gilgit-China.
- Bolan pass connects Queta-Afghanistan.
- Tochi pass connects Pak:-China.
- Length of Silk Route (Korakorum Route) is 965 km.
- Geneva Pact was signed on 14th April, 1988.
- Simla Pact was signed on 3rd July, 1972.
- Numb: of words in anthem=50.
- Numb: of lines in anthem=15.
- Numb: of amendments made 17.
- Numb: of troops in a division are 12000 to 20,000.
- Numb: of troops in brigade is 4000 to 5000.
- Barrages built on Indus = 8.
- Tarbela dam is in NWFP (Abotabad) on Indus river.(Largest)
- Mangla dam is in AJK on Jehlum River(Highest)
- Warsak dam is in NWFP near Peshawar on Kabul river.
- Direct dialing system was introduced b/w Lahore and Rawalpindi for first time in 1964.
- Rivers of Pakistan— Punjab== Ravi+Chanab+Sutlaj.
- Sindh ==Indus, Hub.
- NWFP==Kabul, Sawat, Zhob.
- Baluchistan==Bolan.
- Baluchistan is 43% of total Pak:.
- Geographical divisions of Pak: are 1.Northern Mountains, 2. Western off-shoots of Himalayas, 3. Baluchistan Plateau, 4. Potohar Plateau & Salt range, 5. Lower Indus Plain, 6. Thar desert.
- Pak: has 3 stock exchanges (confirm it).

- Broad Peak I is on Karokarum range.
- Colonel Sher Khan belonged to Sindh Regiment.
- Kot Diji is a fort in Khairpur.
- Ancient mosque of Pak: is at Bhambhor.
- Time taken to sing National Anthem is 1 minute, 20 sec.
- Instruments used are 38.
- Texila is in Punjab and NWFP.
- Rashid Minhas martyred in August 1971.
- Mangla dam is on river Jehlum.
- Old name of Supreme Court is Federal Court.
- 10 persons have received Nishan-e-Hyder.
- Kharif (Summer Season) crops include—Cotton, rice, sugar cane, maize, Jaur and Bajra.
- Rabi (Winter OCT-March) crops are wheat, gram, barley and tobacco.
- Jhat Pat is the old name of Dera Allah Yar.
- There are 7 rivers in Baluchistan.
- Mast Tawakkal was the poet of Balochi.
- Khanpur dam is near Haripur.
- Skardu is also called “Little Tibet”.
- Swat became part of Pakistan in 1969.
- The most precious gemstone “Emerald” are found in Swat.
- Gilgit is the capital of Northern Areas of Pak:
- Khushhal Khan belonged to English period.
- The alphabet of Pushto was prepared by Saifullah.
- First poet of Pushto was Amir Karar.
- Saiful Maluk is near Naran.
- Dera Adam Khan is famous for Gun factory.
- Durand line is b/w Peshawar and Afghanistan.
- Pakistan Forest Institution is located in Peshawar.
- Bala Hassan Fort was built by Babrat at Peshawar.
- Saidu Sharif is a lake in NWFP.
- British took Peshawar from Sikhs.
- Population-wise NWFP stands 3rd.
- Area-wise it is 4th.
- Lands down Bridge connect Sukkur with Rohri.

- Guddu Barrage was completed in 1932.
- Real name of Qalandar Lal Shahbaz is Shaikh Usman Marvindi.
- In 1973 constitution there are 290 articles.
- Pak: comprises of 61% of mountainous area.
- National Assembly has 342 seats & Senate has 100 seats with 14 for each province.
- Provincial Assembly seats Punjab=371, Sindh=168, NWFP=124, Baluchistan=65.
- Name of Ustad Bukhari is Syed Ahmed Shah.
- Real name of Shaikh Ayaz is Shaikh Mubarak.
- Barrages on Indus are Toonsa, Jinnah, Sukkur, Gudo, Kotri & Ghulam Mohd.:
- Ports and harbours are Kimari (Kar:), Bin Qasim (Kar:),
- Jinnah Naval Base (ormara), Gawadar (Baluc:), Panjgore (Baluch:).
- Deserts of Pak: Thar (Sindh), Thal (Punjab), Cholistan (Punjab).
- Famous glaciers are Siachen, Batura, Baltoro.
- K2 (Karakorum Range) with 8610 meters.
- Mountain Ranges are Himaliya, Koradoram, Hindu Kash, Sulaiman and Salt Range.
- Tomb of Babur is in Kabul.
- Real name of Noor Jahan (Wife of Jahangir) was Mehrun Nisa.
- NADRA was setup in Feb: 16, 2000.
- The master plan of Islamabad was prepared in 1960 by MIS Constructinos Doxiades (of Greek).
- National Institute of Oceanlogy Karachi =1982.
- Pak: test fired Ghauri missile in April 6, 1998.
- First nuclear reactor was setup in Karachi.
- Pak:’s first agriculture university setup in Faisalabad.
- Chomas festival is held in Kalash valley near Chitral.
- Nearest provincial capital from Islamabad is Peshawar.
- Tomb of Hamayoon is in Delhi.
- Tomb of Jahangir is at Lahore.
- National Assembly has 60 women seats.
- National anthem was written in 1954.
- Gandhara civilization discovered from Texila.
- Social Action Plan launched in 1992-93.

- Rahmat Ali suggested name of Pakistan on 28th Jan: 1933 in “Now or Never” pamphlet in London.
- Rehmat Ali was born in 1893 in a village Mohar district Hoshiyarpur (East Punjab).
- Rahmat Ali died at the age of 58 in 1951 and was buried in Cambridge University.
- Ancient name of Peshawar was Phushkalvati.
- India framed its constitution in 1950.
- Kara korum Highway (Silkroute) B/w Pak: & China was completed on 18th June, 1978.
- Jamrood Fort (Peshawar) was built by General Hari Singh Nalwa in 1836.
- Landi Khani is the end of the main line of Railway system of Pakistan.
- Cholistan desert is in Bahawlpur district.
- Harpa is in Sahiwal.
- Bhambhore is in Thatta.
- Firdousi, the Persian poet (Shah Nama) was the member of Sultan Mehmood’s court.
- Tomb of Baba Farid is in Pak Patan.
- Tomb of Sachal is in Ranipur.
- Nishtar Hospital is the largest hospital in Pakistan and was built in 1953.
- A.H means Anne Hegirae (Latin Term) =13th Sep: 622 A.D.
- Nanga Parbat is situated in Himalayan.
- Total arable land of Pakistan is 27%.
- Pakistan is situated at the West End of the Indo Gangetic.
- Wakhan separates Pakistan from Tajikistan.
- Hindu-kush range is also known as Little Pamirs.
- Sub-Himalya is also known as Siwaliks.
- The Sindh Sagar Doab is also known as Thal Desert.
- Takt-I-Suleman is the highest peak of Sulaiman Mountains.
- The length of Indus River is 2900 km.
- Six barrages are constructed on the River Indus.
- Hispar Glaciers is located in Hunza.
- The famous Umar Kot fort was built in 1746.
- Katch and Gawadar are the districts of Makran Division.

- Punjgore is the district of Makran division.
- Meaning of Quetta is fort.
- Gomal River is in NWFP.
- The total length of coastline of Pakistan is 1046.
- Cease Fire line came into existence in 1949.
- Pakistan can be divided into six natural regions.
- High of K2 is 8611 Meters.
- The coldest place in Pakistan is Sakardu.
- Most of the Hosiery Industry is located in Karachi.
- The Heavy Mechanical complex was established with the help of China at Taxila.
- The first Census in the subcontinent took place in the year 1901.
- Wheat is the major Kharif Crop of Pakistan.
- Kotli is the city of Azad Kashmir.
- The SOS village built in Faisalabad.
- Pakistan celebrated Quaid's year in 2001.
- Pakistani Cricketer Saeed Anwar declared to join Afghan Jihad.
- Maulana Shibly wrote books on Islamic History.
- The first translation of the Holy Quran was in Sindhi.
- Qutab Minar is in Delhi.
- Cholistan Desert is in Bahawalpur.
- Pakistan can be divided per climate into 4 regions.
- Hashim Shah wrote Sassi Punnu.
- The British Communal Award was announced in 1932.
- Land between two rivers is called Do, aba.
- Shah Jahan Constructed Jamia Masjid Thatta.
- Sindh River flows from Bolan River.
- Kohat is the oldest cantonment of Pakistan.
- Muslims were interested in the art of Calligraphy.
- The length of Durand Line is 2240 km.
- The length of Pakistan's common border with Iran is 805 km.
- Chinese province adjoining Pakistan is Sinkiang.
- Jinnah Barrage is originated on the river Sindh.
- The height of Tarbela Dam is 500 feet.
- Wah city of Pakistan is linked with cement, arms and ammunition industry.
- Sukkur barrage is completed in 1932.

- Khanpur Dam is near Islamabad.
- Simly Lake is near Islamabad.
- Tanda Dam is located in NWFP.
- Khanpur Dam irrigates Attock and Abbotabad.
- Sassi was born in Bhutta Wahan.
- Baba Farid Shakar Gunj died at Pakpattan in 1265.
- Nishtar hospital is the largest hospital in Pakistan.
- Sahiwal is the new name of 'Montgomery'.
- Noor Mahal is located at Bahawalpur.
- The founder of Suharwardi silsila in Pakistan is Rukn-e-Alam.
- Baheshti Darwaza is located in Pakpattan.
- The tomb of Anarkali is situated in at Lahore.
- Shahjehan built Shalimar Garden.
- Hazrat Data Gunj Baksh came in Lahore in 1039 A.D. from the city of Ghazni.
- Minar-e-Pakistan is also called Minto park
- Data Ganj Baksh is the author of Kashful Mahjoob.
- Badshaahi mosque was built in 1674.
- The construction of Islamabad began in 1952.
- Sher Shah built G.T. Road.
- Imperial Highway is the old name of G.T. Road.
- Karakoram highway passes through 3 ranges.
- Nanga Parbat is commonly known as Killer Mountain.
- Karakoram highway was completed in 1978.
- Karakoram was completed in the total period of 20 years.
- The word Karakoram means 'crumbling rock'.
- Karakoram is a Turkish word.
- Karakoram highway passes through khunjrab pass.
- Punial is said to be the place where 'heaven and earth meet'.
- Siachin glacier is located near Astor.
- Hunza is called real Shangrilla.
- Khyber Pass connects Gilgit with Chitral.
- Totally Punjab has 8 divisions.
- The contribution of forestry to the agriculture sector is 0.4%.
- Use of Boron and Zink can improve cotton yield.
- National Arid and Land Development and Research Institute is located at

Islamabad.

- Arid Zone Research Centre of PARC is situated at Quetta.
- Thar Coalfield is the biggest coalfield of Pakistan.
- An M-1 motorway is Islamabad-Peshawar.
- NEC (company) set up Pakistan's first T.V. station.
- 3 radio stations were working at the time of partition.
- Total length of Indus Highway is
- The new name of Debal is 'Bhanbhore'.
- Gharo Creek is a lake.
- Kalakot Fort is situated near Thatta.
- Ranjit Singh sold Kashmir for 75 Lakhs.
- Poonch, a state of Kashmir, fought with Dogra by obtaining arms from tribal areas.
- 10 seats are reserved for non-muslims in National Assembly.
- Frank Meseri was the first C-in-C of Armed Forces.
- The religion of Tamil is Hinduism.
- There is only one female university in Pakistan.
- Kohat is the oldest cantonment of the country.
- Shalimar Garden was built in 1642 A.D.
- Faisalabad is commonly known as little Manchester.
- Harrappa is located at Sahiwal.
- The tomb of Jehangir is located at Shahdara.
- Tomb of Noor Jehan is located at Lahore.
- Attock Fort was built by Akbar.
- Heer Ranjha was written by Waris Shah.
- Sohni Mahiwal was written by Hashim Shah.
- Sindh is called Bab-ul-Islam.
- Chack was the father of Raja Dahir.
- Keti Bunder is the name of a coastal area.
- French Beach is located at Karachi.
- Ranikot Fort is located near Hyderabad.
- Kotri barrage was built in 1955.
- Al Mawardi was born in Basra.
- Nizam-ul-Mulk Tusi was famous for his wisdom.
- "USA is ruled by a power elite," said C. Wright Mills.

- Hub dam supplies electricity to Sindh.
- The number of divisions in the province of Sindh is five.
- Total districts in the province of Sindh are 22.
- Naib Subedar is the lowest commissioned officer of Pakistan Army.
- River Kabul joins Indus river at Attock.
- Meerani Dam is under construction near Turbat.
- Chashma right bank canal on the Indus River provides water for Jhelum River.
- Jinnah station was established in continent Asia on January 25th, 1991.
- National institute of silicon technology was established in 1991.
- Rawalpindi, a region of Punjab, is free from the problem of water logging.
- Jhelum River joins Chenab River near Trimmu.
- River Ravi originates in the Indian state of Hamachel Pradesh.
- Chashma barrage was built in 1971 on river Indus.
- Warsak dam was built in 1960 on river Kabul.
- Rawal dam was built in 1965 on river Kurang.
- Pakistan's oldest archaeological site is situated near Larkana.
- Ayoub Park covers an area of 2300 acres.
- Khewra is the main source of gypsum in Pakistan.
- Sainadak is famous for copper, silver and gold.
- Attock oil refinery is located in Rawalpindi.
- 43% of the gas is obtained from Sui.
- Peshawar means 'city of flowers'.
- Lahore Fort was built in 1560.
- National singer, Noor Jehan, died on 23rd December, 2000.
- Taxila is located b/w Jehlum and Indus.
- Mahbub-ul-Haq Human Development Center is locates at Islamabad.
- Nasirabad region of Balochistan will be irrigated through Kachi cananl.
- The district of the country having lowest population density is: Kharan
- In violation of Indus Basin Treaty 1960, India has constructed Wullar barrage on River Jhelum.
- Water -flows of the river are diverted to Wuller Barrage through the construction of Kishanganga Dam.
- India is constructing Kishanganga Dam in Baramula.
- India has constructed "Baglihar Dam" in occupied Kashmir's district of Doda.

- AKHORI DAM. Location. Across Nandnakas near Akhori village about 28 KM east of Attock

Punjab.

- Wakhan is a narrow strip of land which separates Afghanistan from Pakistan.